

Graphene crossed architecture for molecular hybrid system

by

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ABSTRACT

Due to excellent electrical, mechanical, optical properties of graphene owing to its unique band structure and two dimensionality, there is rush to make graphene based devices. Here we propose and prepare a very simple still yet unexplored kind of macroscopic size device which is made by placing two graphene ribbons (few mm^2) perpendicular to each other. We show that the intersection of the two ribbons, gives very high mobility as compared to standard single ribbons and also coupling between these two ribbons is confirmed by Raman spectroscopy. In the second part we propose to fabricate a graphene hybrid system by placing molecules which are optically active or eclectically active in between the intersection of the two layers. The characterization of such functionalization is described in this part.

1. Introduction: Graphene from fabrication to devices

Graphene, a monolayer of carbon atoms, is a truly two-dimensional structure stable under ambient conditions, first obtained by micromechanical cleavage of graphite (A.K Geim 2004). Since then it activated an enormous research interest as it shows outstanding mechanical, structural and electronic properties (Daniel R. Cooper 2011). In this chapter we will present its electronic band structure, then discuss about the CVD (Chemical Vapour Deposition) growth of graphene which is a promising technique for high quality large scale synthesis of graphene. Later on we discuss how to characterize the graphene using Raman spectroscopy and transport measurements. Lastly we discuss about making new functional materials using graphene hybrids (Manuel Lopes 2010), which is a kind of forming molecular junction based on graphene.

1.1 Graphene electronic band structure

Graphene is a planar sheet of carbon atoms arranged in hexagonal rings, which form a honey-comb lattice (see Fig. 1.1). One can also describe it as a system of connected benzene rings stripped out from their hydrogen atoms. In terms of Molecular Orbital Theory its atomic structure is characterized by two types of C-C bonds (σ , π), constructed from the four valence orbitals of carbon atom ($2s$, $2p_x$, $2p_y$, $2p_z$), where the z direction is perpendicular to the sheet of graphene. Each carbon atom bonds to the 3 carbon neighbors *via* in-plane σ -bonds formed from sp^2 hybridized orbitals (orbitals formed from one s -orbital and two p -orbitals), while the fourth, remaining p_z -orbital gives rise to a highly delocalized π -orbital and its electron is free to move. The bonding π - and antibonding π^* -orbitals form the wide electronic valence and conduction bands.

Graphene has two identical carbon atoms in each unit cell and thus two equivalent atom sub-lattices: A and B (indicated by different colours in Fig. 1.1.a). As a consequence of the high lattice symmetry the band structure of graphene at low energies has a linear conical shape (Fig. 1.1b). This is a remarkable difference from the usual parabolic energy-momentum relation in conventional semiconductors. In graphene the conduction and valence bands touch each other in one point at the 6 corners of the two-dimensional hexagonal Brillouin zone and create the zero band gap of this semi-metal. Due to symmetry only two out of six points, (K, K'), are essentially different, while the rest four are equivalent to them. This leads to the so called valley degeneracy. The residual point, where the conduction and the valence band touches, is called the Dirac point.

The dispersion relation $E(k)$ in the vicinity of Dirac points (K, K') fulfills the following equation:

$$E(k) = \pm \hbar v_f \sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2} \quad (1.1)$$

Where a + sign corresponds to the conduction band and a – sign to the valence band. The group velocity around the Dirac point (the Fermi velocity) is $v_f = 1 \times 10^6 \text{ m / s}$.

Figure 1.1:(a) Hexagonal lattice of graphene. Different color of carbon atom indicates the two identical sublattices, labeled A and B. The grey area marks the unit cell; d_{c-c} gives the distance between two neighboring carbons. (b) The band structure of graphene. The zoomed region presents the linear shape of conduction and valence band connected through the Dirac point.

1.2 Synthesis

A repeatable synthesis of graphene *via* mechanical exfoliation was realized by Novoselov *et al.* in 2004 (A.K Geim 2004). This technique has been applied since then, along with efforts to produce large-scale graphene. Some physical and chemical methods to produce graphene are presented here.

1.2.1 Mechanical exfoliation

Highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) consists of many graphene sheets weakly bonded together by Van der Waals force. Scotch tape is used to peel off the multiple layers of graphene from the bulk graphite. Afterwards, the tape is gently rubbed on top of a substrate with soft tweezers to prevent damaging the graphene flakes and this tape is then carefully removed. This successful technique can provide high structural and electronic quality flakes as thin as single and few layers of graphene. However, it can only produce small flakes of graphene of the order of $10 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter suitable for academic research but not for industrial applications as the deposition of thin layers is laborious and time-consuming.

1.2.2 Epitaxial growth

A commonly used technique to produce graphene is epitaxy on the surface of silicon carbide (SiC) wafers, which produces large-area graphene (J Hass 2008). This is realized by annealing SiC at high temperature ($>1250 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) in ultra-high vacuum (UHV) or argon atmosphere. This process sublimates sufficient Si to leave behind a carbon rich surface, resulting in the growth of 1 to 3 high quality graphene layers. The number of graphene layers is determined by the decomposition temperature used and the amount of Si evaporated.

Even though this process looks attractive, a good control on the number of graphene layers has to be resolved. Another issue is the strong interaction between graphene and SiC and large difference in the thermal expansion coefficient of graphene and SiC that affect the electronic properties of graphene. Therefore, transport measurements on epitaxial graphene differ greatly from the one of mechanically exfoliated graphene.(J Hass 2008)

1.2.3 CVD growth on transition metals

Graphene monolayer can be formed on the surface of transition metals *via* chemical vapor deposition (CVD). These are produced either by thermal decomposition of hydrocarbons undergoing a dehydrogenation process in which the carbon atoms rearrange into a honeycomb lattice (Xuesong Li 2009) or by controlled segregation in which carbon atoms out diffuse from the bulk of the substrate(A.Reina 2008). Further details about this approach are later discussed in this thesis.

1.3 Characterization

A number of techniques have been developed to characterize graphene, but here we are going to discuss most important ones.

1.3.1 Microscopy

Here we are going to have a fast look on various microscopy techniques involved in the characterization of graphene.

Atomic Force Microscopy is often used to measure nanoscale thicknesses such as distinguishing a monolayer from a few-layer graphene. However but this inaccuracy on the thickness of graphene due to bad coupling to the substrate or we have very uneven surface.

Scanning Electron Microscopy is generally used to identify the grain boundaries of graphene, wrinkles on the graphene layer, number of layers, defects or adsorbates and also to confirm the continuity of growth. However, this technique is quite destructive as during scanning we generally burn the graphene due to the exposure to high energy electron beam.

Scanning Tunneling Microscopy on graphene has reported some pentagon, heptagon and deformed hexagon along the grain boundaries of graphene, but this technique is very time consuming.

Using an optical microscope we can identify the number of layers of graphene on SiO₂. The contrast depends on the thickness of SiO₂, the wavelength of light used (P.Blake 2007).This feature of graphene is useful for the quick identification of few to single layer graphene sheets.

Figure 1.2: Multilayer graphene sheet on Si/SiO₂ substrate showing different optical contrast at different wavelength and thickness of substrate used. In a) contrast showing number of layers as indicated by arrow and this is the best thickness to obtain a strong optical contrast for graphene. In b) numbers show the number of layers using the best suited wavelength. In c) we are not able to see anything for this oxide thickness. Image adapted from (P.Blake 2007).

1.3.2 Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy is an important characterization tool for carbon-based materials used to probe the phonon spectrum of graphene. Raman spectroscopy is a spectroscopic technique based on inelastic scattering of monochromatic light, usually from a laser source. Inelastic scattering means that the frequency of photons in monochromatic light changes upon interaction with a sample. Photons of the laser light are diffused by the sample at a different wavelength. Frequency of the reemitted photons is shifted up (anti-Stokes line) or down (Stokes line) in comparison with original monochromatic frequency, which is called the Raman effect. This shift provides information about vibrational, rotational and other low frequency transitions in molecules. Raman spectroscopy of graphene can be used to determine the number of graphene layers and stacking order (using polarized light) as well as density of defects and impurities. The three most prominent peaks in the Raman spectrum of graphene and other graphitic materials are the G band at $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the 2D band at $\sim 2680\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the disorder-induced D band at $\sim 1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The G band results from in-plane vibration of sp² carbon atoms and is the most prominent feature of most graphitic materials. The 2D band arises as a result of a two phonon resonance process, involving phonons near the K point, and is very prominent in graphene as compared to bulk graphite. (L.M.Malard 2009).

The D band is induced by defects in the graphene lattice (corresponding to the in-plane optical phonons near the K point), and is not seen in highly ordered graphene layers. The intensity ratio of the D and 2D band can be used to characterize the number of defects in a graphene sample.

Figure 1.3: Layer dependence of graphene Raman spectrum. Raman spectra $N=1-4$ on Si/SiO_2 substrate. Fig. adapted from (Yu 2010).

The line shape of the 2D peak, as well as its intensity relative to the G peak, can be used to characterize the number of layers of graphene present as illustrated in Figure 1.3. Single-layer graphene is characterized by a very sharp, symmetric, Lorentzian 2D peak with intensity greater than twice the G peak {FWHM (Full Width at Half Maxima) for single layer graphene is 24 cm^{-1} }. As the number of layers increases the 2D peak involves more than one Lorentzian and becomes broader, less symmetric and decreases in intensity.

1.4 Transport measurements in graphene

The basic graphene device resembles a field effect transistor (FET) and is schematically drawn in Fig. 1.4(a). Graphene is deposited on a silicon dioxide (SiO_2) layer, connected to source and drain electrodes, with a heavily doped silicon substrate as the gate electrode. Applying a gate voltage creates the potential drop across the SiO_2 insulating layer. Like in a capacitor the gate voltage induces surface charge density, according to the equation:

$$n = e\epsilon_r V_g / te = \alpha V_g \quad (1.2)$$

Where ϵ_0 is the permittivity of vacuum ($\epsilon_0 \sim 8.854 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ F/m}$), ϵ_r is the relative permittivity of SiO_2 (the literature value is $\epsilon_r = 3.9$), t is the thickness of SiO_2 layer (in our case $t=285 \text{ nm}$) and e is the electron charge ($e=1.6 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ C}$). After substituting the values we find the proportionality coefficient between induced charge carriers and the applied gate voltage: $\alpha \cong 7.2 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ V}^{-1}$.

With changing the gate voltage we modify the charge carrier density in the graphene (graphene acts as the second parallel plate of the capacitor) and therefore we can tune its Fermi level. In neutral graphene the Fermi level lies at the Dirac point. Because it is a single point in the band structure, it generates zero density of states. This means that there are no states to occupy and hence there are no carriers, which could contribute to the electronic transport (at the Dirac point carrier concentration vanishes, $n=0$). As a result, for the Fermi level at the Dirac point graphene exhibits a large resistivity (order of few $\text{k}\Omega$).

Figure 1.4.: Structure of graphene FET device (a). Set up used by us to measure the resistivity. In (b) typical graphene resistivity as a function of gate voltage V_g is presented. Maximum of resistivity occurs when Fermi level lies at the Dirac point for which $n = 0$ (off state of the FET). Away from the Dirac point resistivity decreases rapidly (on state of the FET).

The Dirac point separates the region of electrons conduction (when the Fermi level lies within the conduction band) from the region where transport is governed by holes (when Fermi level lies within the valence band). With the back-gate voltage, we shift the Fermi level away from the Dirac point (into hole or electron conduction regime) the resistance decreases with the increase of gate voltage. This is related to the increase of carrier concentration, which contributes to the transport. The described behavior of the graphene resistance at different gate voltages is given in fig. 1.4b

The Dirac voltage V_{Dirac} is identified as the gate voltage for which the maximum of resistivity occurs. In neutral graphene $V_{Dirac} = 0V$, but for doped graphene it is shifted depending on the doping level (here the dopants may be moisture or molecules). Dopants shift the Fermi level out from the Dirac neutrality point and hence the maximum of the resistance occurs at the gate voltage which compensates the charges of dopants. To calculate the charge carrier density at various gate voltages, equation Eq. 1.2 needs to be shifted by the Dirac voltage V_{Dirac}

$$n = \alpha(V_g - V_{Dirac}) \quad (1.3)$$

The symmetrical shape of the energy dispersion relation $E(k)$ for the conduction and valence band implies equal group velocities for electrons and for holes. In ideal graphene (no defects or impurities) or in graphene with isotropic scattering, when scattering mechanisms affect the carriers (electrons or holes) with the same strength, no matter of their charge sign, the drift velocity of carriers V_{drift} (the average velocity that a carrier attains due to an electric field, $V_{drift} = \mu_i E$) is the same for electrons and for holes. As a consequence the electron mobility μ_e is equal to the hole mobility μ_h .

This can be verified experimentally by measuring the electrical conductivity as a function of gate voltage:

$$\sigma(V_g) = n_i(V_g) e \mu_i \quad (1.4)$$

where $n_i(V_g)$ is the concentration of carriers of type i (i = electrons; holes), calculated from Eq. 1.3. An example of conductivity measurements is presented in Fig. 1.5 There, away from the Dirac point we can see a linear dependence of the conductivity from the gate voltage. The slope of the linear fit for holes (α) and for electrons (β) is different, here $|\beta/\alpha| \cong 0.6$. The ratio between mobility of electrons and holes is not universal and depends on the quality of graphene and also on the substrate.

Mobility reflects the strength of scattering mechanism, which includes the intrinsic scattering (like scattering on phonons) and extrinsic (scattering on defects, impurities or adsorbates). The values of reported mobility in graphene at room temperature show large dispersion (from 1000 up to 70000 cm^2/Vs) (A.K. Geim 2004; K.I. Bolotin 2008), depending on whether it is exfoliated, CVD or suspended graphene

1.5 Graphene hybrids

The concept of hybrid system extends to situations when despite the absence of physical or chemical bond between the two (or more) compounds, at least one of the compound's properties influences those of the other compounds leading to combined or novel function. Here our hybrid system is graphene + molecules. In this kind of systems, Strong fluorescence quenching of nearby nano objects has been observed and strong enhancement in Raman signal too (GERS: Graphene enhanced Raman Spectroscopy) (Ling 2010), which can be used in molecule detection. Interestingly this GERS can be modulated by tuning the carrier density in graphene which shows the advantage of coupling nano-objects to a semi-metal.

Figure 1.6: Grafting of pyrene substituted TbPc_2 molecule over the graphene which shows GERS.

Now a natural question arises: what kind of molecules will be interesting for us, so preserving graphene's unique electronic transport property which requires non-covalent functionalization. In this view, molecules having aromatic groups such as aryl, phenyl or pyrene ones offer the possibility for π -stacking functionalization to graphene (e.g. TbPc_2 (Manuel Lopes 2010) can be a very good example)

2. Crossbar: A Novel Architecture

The exceptional high mobility of graphene has attracted much interest in the scientific community and many potential applications have been proposed. Till now we have seen graphene based transistor (Schwierz 2010), transparent conducting electrode (Byung-Jae Kim 2010) *etc.* All these devices have been prepared so as to take advantage of single layer graphene's exceptional optical, mechanical, electrical properties, but it seems very few devices have been prepared by playing with the graphene sheets to make a new kind of geometry, which may give rise to some interesting new phenomena.

Here we propose a very simple, macroscale sized device prepared by placing two graphene ribbons perpendicular to each other, which we call Cross bar from now on in this report. Below is fig.2.1 showing the first crossbar we made.

Now preparation of this device raises a very simple question. What for?

Figure.2.1: Graphene crossbar

This graphene crossbar was prepared by placing two graphene ribbons (mm in size) perpendicular to each other on top of Si/SiO₂ substrate. Here the white circle shows the most important part of the device, which will be referred to as intersection of the two ribbons or region of interest or crossbar region

The answer to this question can be given in straight forward two points.

- (i) To understand the transport of charge carrier between graphene layers *i.e.* physical phenomena happening in the region of interest.
- (ii) To use this region of interest as a platform to make graphene hybrid system, with properties which can be tuned by playing with some parameters (e.g. light or electric field)?

Let us discuss these points one by one in detail.

2.1 Transport in Crossbar

In the region of interest, the two ribbons which are placed on each other are separated by very small distance (order of few nm idea given by atomic force microscopy). Now one can ask, what is the coupling between the two layers (are they behaving collectively or separately)? Another worthy question to be asked is that if the below layer screens the above layer (Screens the gate effect because above layer will not be seeing the same field as below layer) or not. These two concepts raised by the special geometry of this device will be dominating the transport of charge carrier from one layer to another.

Our goal is to understand the transport of charge carrier in this device and to provide a theoretical model for this device which can fit the experimental data; also we want to measure the transport properties of this device at very low temperature which may give rise to some interesting results such as the tunnel coupling between the layers.

2.2 Graphene hybrid system

In addition we are also interested in graphene hybrid system. Graphene optical hybrid system has already been reported in the literature (Manuel Lopes 2010) but this type of work is done on single ribbon graphene only. Using the crossbar geometry, our goal is to address the molecules electrically in the region between the intersections of two layers which is not possible on single ribbon. Moreover, the molecules in between the graphene layers will be protected from the environment (oxidation), which is quite interesting for sensitive molecules. Performing Raman and transport measurements will provide insights into the properties of this graphene hybrid.

3. Device fabrication and measurement system

In this chapter we present the procedure of device preparation, pointing out the challenges to overcome and the lines we followed to solve the problems we encountered during experiments. Due to two questions raised by thesis, we divided this chapter into two parts (A and B).

Part A: we give a brief description of CVD (Chemical Vapour Deposition) growth of monolayer graphene and then transfer on to the SiO₂ substrate. We then present the different techniques we used to characterize the sample geometry and quality. In the last section of Part A we present the measurement system and measurement scheme for device electrical characterization.

Part B: we present the molecules we have used and their deposition procedure over single ribbon graphene.

Part A

3.1 CVD growth of graphene

Mechanically exfoliated graphene (A.K Geim 2004) is best in terms of quality but tedious nature of extraction and micron scale flake size limit its implementation. On the other hand CVD grown graphene on Cu is considered to be one of the most promising materials for future graphene application because of its monolayer formation, large size deposition and transferrable nature (Xuesong Li 2009). Here we discuss the different steps involved in this process and mechanism of the growth.

- (i) Copper foil preparation: Copper foil (Alfa Aesar, 99.8%, 25 μ m thick) is cleaned with iso-propanol and then cut into squares (roughly 5 cm \times 2 cm).

Figure 3.1: CVD setup (a). Image of the CVD built by Zheng Han (Ph.D student in our group) showing quartz tube, furnace, exhaust pipe. (b) Block diagram of the CVD setup.

- (ii) Furnace preparation: Once the copper foils have been mounted inside the quartz tube, the vacuum fittings are connected on both sides of the tube. It is important to have a good vacuum (\sim 30mTorr), as gas leaks; especially

oxygen can have an adverse effect on graphene growth. First several purges cycles of 10-30 sccm (Standard Cubic Centimeters per Minute) of Hydrogen (each time pressure rising close to 1 Torr) are performed to remove the contaminants.

- (iii) Foil annealing: the hydrogen flow (Ivan Vlasiouk 2011) is set to 2 sccm, and then the furnace programmed for 1000 °C. It takes about an hour to reach this temperature, and the pressure fluctuates as gases are desorbed from the quartz tube, substrate holder, and copper foils. Once the operating temperature is reached, the foils should be annealed for at least 30min. This helps removing the oxide layer and organic adsorbates from the copper foil as well as it increase the size of crystal grains.
- (iv) Graphene growth: When the annealing is complete, the methane MFC (Mass Flow Controller) is set to 35 sccm and the growth time to about 10min. At this point, the lid to the furnace is opened, which stops the heating elements and the system cools down (1000°C to 300°C in 4 hours). When the temperature reaches 200°C, the pump can be stopped and the system vented. The copper foils, now covered in graphene on all sides, should look bright (fig.3.2b).

Figure 3.2: CVD process a) Showing the growth condition; b) comparison of Cu foil before and after the growth of graphene

3.2 Growth mechanism:

Here an important question arises: why Cu as a substrate? Why not some other substrate is used (e.g. Ni)? If a Cu substrate is used, coverage is monolayer. Using Cu instead of a transition metal to produce only monolayer graphene was the major advance of Li *et al.* (Xuesong Li 2009). The reason why Cu produces a single layer while Ni produces more layers can be understood from the solubility phase diagrams of carbon in the two metals (Fig. (3.3)). In weight percent, the solubility of carbon at the melting point of copper, 1085 °C is only 0.0076%. On the other hand, the solubility of carbon in the transition metal nickel at its melting point of 1455 °C is 0.6 wt%! Even at 1085 °C, this solubility is still orders of magnitude higher than in copper. The carbon solubility at the maximum furnace temperature will determine the amount of carbon contained in the substrate which will desorb or precipitate at the surface as the furnace is cooled. In the case of nickel, carbon is significantly dissolved in the bulk, and then precipitates and graphitizes as the furnace is cooled,

leading to a coverage much greater than a monolayer. Cu, with its lower solubility, can produce uniform monolayer because carbon is not dissolved significantly in the bulk.

Figure 3.3: (a) Phase diagram of C in Ni, (b) Phase diagram of C in Cu, here note that x scale in a and b are completely different.

Till now we have seen the CVD growth of graphene. Now everyone must be curious to know how it looks like and what is the quality of graphene. So to characterize it we have used SEM and Raman spectroscopy as shown in fig.3.4a and 3.4 b. Fig. 3.4a) shows the continuous layer of graphene with some multilayer parts, wrinkles and white spheres contaminants which may be some Cu remaining or most probably dust. Fig.3. 4b shows the flower type growth of the graphene, showing the discontinuity of graphene Fig.3.5 Raman spectra of graphene over the Cu, here the ratio of 2D/G(bands) is important to tell about the quality of graphene. (L.M.Malard 2009), it should be around 2 for good quality graphene..

Also during the growth we found that graphene is not of good quality was confirmed by high sheet resistance (up to 10k Ohms we consider it as good quality) where resistance is measured by electrical setup which is discussed later on. Firstly we found that vacuum of the system was not good so oxygen which is creating defects in the graphene, still we were not able to solve the problem and then we found that Hydrogen gas (Ivan Vlasiouk 2011)(which acts as etchant) was not pure so by replacing the hydrogen bottle, we got the good quality graphene which was confirmed by electrical measurements (low resistance) We found that in the best batch grown by us we have 2D/G ratio almost double which is same as mentioned in the literature.

Figure 3.4: a) SEM image of monolayer graphene on Cu which is showing multilayer and wrinkles and contaminants b) SEM image of flower shaped discontinuous graphene.

It is important to note that while doing Raman we cannot use the green laser, because copper absorbs at this frequency which gives rise to fluorescence blurring the spectrum

Figure 3.5: Raman spectra of Graphene on Cu Here the Raman spectra are taken at laser wavelength 633nm (Red laser), also it is the spectra of best batch of graphene grown by us.

3.3 .Preparation of the crossbar device

Here comes the most crucial part of this thesis *i.e.* the preparation of crossbars, so in this part we will go into the details of the fabrication protocol. One point to be noticed is that the heart of this part is all about taking care of the quality of graphene, which can be defected very easily during the transfer process

3.3.1 Preparation of the silicon substrate

Now why transferring graphene onto Si/SiO₂ substrate? Most fabrication techniques have been developed on Si for application in microelectronics, and so are available for the material. Moreover to make transistor device we need a gate dielectric, which is realized by SiO₂ grown onto degenerately doped silicon wafers. A tricky point is that for clear visibility of graphene over Si/SiO₂ substrate, the thickness of SiO₂ should be either 90nm or 285nm.

Since our motto is to prepare defect free devices, it is essential to have a surface that is free from metallic and organic contaminants so we followed these guidelines (Karen A. Reinhardt 2008).

- (i) The Si/SiO₂ wafer (SiO₂ thickness 285nm ± 5%, orientation <100>, p type degenerately doped, 0.001-0.005 Ωcm) and is spin coated (Spin 150) with 4% PMMA (Poly(methyl methacrylate) solvent is Anisole) at 4000 rpm (rotation per minute) for 60 seconds which gives a thickness of ~100nm. The only purpose was that during cleaving (SCRIBE 100 (JFP Microtechnic)), remaining of Si do not stick to the substrate surface.
- (ii) Now to clean the small square substrate (3 mm), we remove PMMA, by sonicating the sample in an acetone beaker at frequency 35 kHz, power 40W for 3 minutes. Then take it out and wash it with IPA (Propane-2-ol) and then dry it with nitrogen blower.
- (iii) Now put the substrate in a beaker of RBS (surfactant) + DI (deionized water) and did sonication at frequency 35 kHz at power 40W for 3 minutes. This was done to remove the organic dirt. It must be noted that after RBS sonication it was washed with DI (Deionized) water otherwise it leaves dirty marks on it and then dry it with nitrogen blower.
- (iv) Now to get rid of RBS marks completely put the Si substrate into the beaker filled with IPA (Propane-2-ol) and do sonication at frequency 35 kHz, power 40W for 1 minute. Again dry it with Nitrogen blower.
- (v) Lastly we did RIE (reactive Ion Etching) using oxygen as plasma for 5 minutes and this was done to make the surface hydrophilic (because it is changing all organic dirt in CO₂ and leaves dangling bond on silica). This is of great importance while transferring the graphene from the etchant to Si/SiO₂ substrate.

3.3.2 Copper etch:

By CVD we obtain graphene on 3 inches large (square) Cu foil, and then cut a 1cm portion of it. To get bare graphene Cu must be etched away for transfer (fig. 3.6e) onto Si/SiO₂ substrate. If the graphene coated Cu foils is placed in sodium persulfate solution (Na₂(SO₄)₂) {we used 0.84 M} within 12 hours copper is dissolved, but the problem is that graphene will curl up (Indeed it has tendency to stick to itself due to strong Van der Waals forces) and it will not be possible to transfer it. It is worthy to note that since Cu foil has two faces, now the face of the Cu with which is sit to the quartz substrate (backside), has non continuous growth of graphene because gaseous pass unevenly through it. Then we spin coated the above side (PMMA 4% at 4000 RPM) of graphene/Cu. Taking care not to have the polymer run down onto the backside. If the PMMA coats both sides of the square, the etchants will not work as they cannot penetrate PMMA. Bake the PMMA/graphene/Cu directly on a hot plate at 180 °C for 2min. Once the square is cool, cut a few millimeters of the sides to remove any PMMA that has crept onto the backside, and then we oxygen plasma etch the back

side to remove the graphene, Now we cut a dozen small ribbons (2mm×4mm) of size, Keeping the PMMA-coated side up, we place the ribbons into the etchant solution. If plasma etching has not been done it then etching process will take 3 to 4 days by the above etchant.

3.3.3 Graphene transfer

In about 12 hours in $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$, the solution color changes and a transparent square of PMMA is visible floating on the surface. The graphene is stuck to the underside of the floating PMMA. Delicately use a plastic spoon to fish the PMMA square out of the etchant solution and transfer it into a clean deionized water bath. Transfer several times to fresh water baths to disperse etchant solution remaining on the PMMA/graphene as shown in fig.3 6a and 3.6b. Now the PMMA/graphene can be transferred onto the substrate (Si/SiO₂). Dip the substrate into the water bath and delicately approach it towards the bottom side of the PMMA/graphene square. Gently pull it out, taking care to avoid folding. Because we have made the substrate hydrophilic by plasma cleaning just before, the graphene + PMMA (hydrophobic) floating on water will sit onto the substrate with water underneath which allows to adjust the ribbon position. Bake the PMMA/graphene/substrate for an hour at 180°C to remove any residual water. Then dissolve the PMMA in acetone and

Figure 3.6 a) transfer of graphene +PMMA from the etchant with the spoon made from a pipette; b) graphene+ PMMA floating in DI (deionized) water after many washings; c) Graphene ribbon on Si substrate after PMMA has been removed;(width of the ribbon 1mm) d) showing the cross bar by transferring second ribbon over the first one. Here contrast is different because we use different illumination to get best image.e) Schematics of transfer process.

rinse with iso-propanaol. It must be noted that during that step, graphene is very thin and has a tendency to stick with itself, so during the transfer we folded the graphene many times. Moreover if the washing is not good, some ions will remain stuck to the graphene which is clearly seen in fig.3.6d.

Till now we have prepared the single ribbon on the Si/SiO₂ substrate as shown in fig.3 6c. In order to make crossbars, the deposition of the second ribbon is somehow different as described now.

We already have some graphene+ PMMA ribbon floating into the etchant (as we cut many ribbons), so clean this ribbon as mentioned earlier. Then dip the as already fabricated single ribbon sample into the water bath containing the second ribbon and delicately approach it to the PMMA/graphene ribbon to make a cross as shown in fig3.6d.

Now this transfer of the second layer is very problematic, because oxygen plasma is forbidden as it removes the graphene, so now the surface is hydrophobic so as graphene+ PMMA is. For the first ribbon on fig3 6c we were being helped by hydrophilicity of the substrate, but this time the second ribbon does not stick to graphene, so much precautions and practice are needed to manage it .

Lastly we want to characterize the crossbar, our intention was used to measure the interlayer distance.

Figure 3.7 AFM (Atomic Force Microscope) topographic images: a) Showing the edge of the ribbon while white rectangle showing the region made by us to measure the distance, the scale bar on the right side showing the height,. b) AFM image over the surface of sample

During AFM measurements we found that the distance between two ribbons, as varying from 1.1nm to 1.4 nm, which indicates the presence of some impurity in between the ribbon and substrate. In 3.7b) we see change in color at some regions which is due to the wrinkles (white lines) and to holes between graphene grains (dark lines).Also we can see that edge of the graphene is very rough as it is cut by hand with scissors (Fig. 3.7a).

3.3.4 Deposition of the electrodes:

To make the measurements we have to make electrodes over it so that we can do measurements, so in this section we will be talking about this.

3.3.4.1 Preparation of the sample

To make crossbar we have to deposit the electrodes over the sides of the ribbons, taking care not to connect the intersection of them (or it would be shunted). Considering the macroscale size of our device, we used a mechanical mask to do this job. The advantages of using a mechanical mask is that it does not require any resist so it is a clean way to make electrodes without putting any chemicals on graphene, very easy to handle, less time consuming, cheaper as compared to the standard lithography process.

Figure 3.8: sequential steps to deposit the Ti/Au electrode over the single ribbon (c) and the crossbar (d).

These mechanical mask are made of aluminum which are rectangle in size (5 cm×4 cm) with parallel cuts of width varying from 1 mm to 2 mm. First of all we put our sample over the Scotch tape as shown in fig.3.8a) and then we adjust the mechanical mask in such a manner that only end part of the ribbon is exposed and rest of the parts we cover with scotch tape. In this way our sample is ready for the deposition of electrodes. To deposit the electrodes over the single ribbon, follow the same process as described above, the only difference is that you have to align your mask in different way and after deposition you will get device as shown in fig.3.8c.

3.3.4.2 Deposition

For the deposition of electrodes we used electron beam evaporation (Plassys, Nanofab) in which we applied a strong electric field to extract electrons from a filament which strike the metal crucible (Au, Ti are the ones used here) and melts it. This takes place in a vacuum of $\sim 10^{-7}$ mbar to ensure contamination free deposition. To improve the adhesion of gold to the silica substrate and graphene, a thin layer of titanium (~ 3 to ~ 5 nm) is deposited first and then a gold layer of ~ 50 to ~ 60 nm is deposited. The evaporation rates and deposition thicknesses are following: Ti: 0.15 nm/s, 3 nm; Au: 0.2 nm/s, 55 nm. As a result, our sample is covered with a thin layer of metal with desired thickness.

Now our device is fully operational and ready to use as shown in fig. 3.8d.

3.4 Measurement setup

One of the objectives of this thesis is an investigation of the transport properties of this special kind of device from room to low temperatures.

3.4.1 Probe station

To measure the transport properties we made our device in a FET geometry in which the two gold contacts act as Source (S) and Drain (D), 285 nm thick SiO_2 acts as gate dielectric and gate voltage is applied on the doped silicon substrate. For these measurements we used TTP4 Probe Station (Lakeshore Cryogenics) which can be used for non-destructive electrical testing of devices on full wafers up to 2 inches in diameter, down to low temperature (1K) (fig. 3.9).

Figure 3.9; Signal connection, image taken from TTP4 operational guide.

Signals for testing samples and reading sample responses are routed between the signal connector and the sample *via* the probe arm and probe terminated by a copper tip to manage the electrical contact onto our gold electrodes. This route is illustrated by the blue path in the diagram. The triax sample holders allow the user to apply gate voltage to the sample holder. These signals are routed from the bottom of the chamber to the sample holder, as shown by the red path. In this set up we have four arms; one of them is shown in fig. 3.9. To ensure good measurements, sample shall not move and also shall be electrically connected for the gate effect, for that we applied some conducting silver paint (RS 186-3600) to the back of the sample and glued it to the sample holder.

In layman words this probe station is just a medium to connect our device to the voltage source and lock in amplifier by using tip whose diameter is $10\mu\text{m}$. Here we will be conducting 2 probe and 4 probe measurement but what is the difference in 2 probe and 4 probe measurements

Difference between 2P and 4P:

With the 2 point method, current and voltage are measured in the same wire. So, the measured voltage is added with the potential difference created into the wires (Cause of Ohms Law: $U=RI$). For high resistivity (from 1M ohm/sq), this method can be used because contact resistance is negligible. For low resistivity measurement, this method will be not accurate because contact resistance will very close to sample resistance.

Figure 3.10: Setup for 2 probe and 4 probe measurements

That is why, for low resistivity, the best method is the 4 point probing. Current is sent in two probes and voltage is measured by two other probes. Since, no current is flowing through the voltage probe which prevents additional voltage related to contact resistance and allows measuring the real voltage within the sample so measurement will be more accurate.

Figure 3.11: 2 probe and 4 probe measurements for the same sample

To confirm this observation we did 2 probe and 4 probe measurement over the same device, and fig. 3.11 showing us that ratio of on state resistance for 2 probe over 4 probe is 2, i.e. we remove the influence of the contact resistance of the device. in case of four probe measurements.

3.4.2 AC measurements

In AC measurements excitation signal is applied from Lock in amplifier (SR-830) and back gate voltage is applied by voltage source (Keithely 6430) as shown in fig. 3.11a. In AC measurements we use lock in amplifier to get rid of noise. 2 probe and 4 probe measurements for the AC circuit is shown in fig.3.12a

3.4.2.1 Lock in amplifier:

Now since we are applying very low bias voltages, the signal to noise ratio is very low. So to get rid of this problem we used a lock in amplifier which relies on orthogonality of sinusoidal functions. Specifically, when a sinusoidal function of frequency ν is multiplied by another sinusoidal function of frequency μ not equal to ν and integrated over a time much longer than the period of the two functions, the result is zero. In the case when μ is equal to ν , and the two functions are in phase, the average value is equal to half of the product of the amplitudes, so by this way we improve the signal to noise ratio. In our case we excite the device with a sinusoidal signal and using this orthogonality we measure the signal at the excitation frequency and rest of the signal is being removed.

The only problem with AC is that when we do not have good contact then phase of the signal is reading wrong values so resistance get by us, is just artifact of the experiment

3.4.3 DC measurements

In case of DC measurements the bias voltage (0.1 to 0.2 Volts) is applied between Drain and Source by the Voltage source (Keithely 6430) and gate voltage is applied by voltage source (Keithely 6430) as shown in fig. 3.12b.

The most important settings in the measurement setup can be controlled by computer with the aid of a LabView script (written by Adrien Allain and Zheng Han). It involves recording the amplitude and the phase of detected signal, the gate voltage, leak current, differential resistance.

Figure 3.12 a and b showing circuit diagrams for AC (two probe and four probe) and DC measurements. Experimental implementation of 2 probe and 4 probe is represented in fig.3.10

In DC measurements which does not involve any phase, but the problem with DC measurements is that it is not good for systems when we have low signal to noise ratio.

Part B

3.5 Deposition of molecules over single ribbons

To make graphene hybrid systems we want to deposit molecules over it in a controlled manner. Here we started first of all molecules on the single ribbon to see the interaction between ribbon and molecule. Till yet we have used four molecules as mentioned earlier. Here we will be using 2 molecules only because other two molecules show huge fluorescence. Infact TPPZn also show huge fluorescence.

3.5.1 Deposition:

- (i) TPyOs: Weighted 0.002g of the TPyOs and dissolved it into 1 mL of acetone (0.00182M), initial color was reddish brown, this we called it as mother solution(m) then diluted it to 100 and 1000 times to make m1 and m2 solution. Pour one to two drops over the single ribbon with the help of pipette and then wait for 30 seconds ,rinse it with the acetone so that molecules do not aggregate. We find that with this concentration(m2) there are no molecules over it (by Raman spectroscopy, we find no shift in molecule signature) so we switch to m1 solution and then this time we find the cluster over the ribbon so to remove the cluster we did sonication for 10 seconds we also tried drop casting method and deposition by spin(spin coating)
- (ii) TPPZn: Weight 0.0036g of the molecule and dissolved it into the 1 ml of DCM(Di-CholoroMethane) (0.005M), initial color was dark pink, this we called it as mother solution this we called it as mother solution(m) then diluted it to 100 and 1000 times to make m1 and m2 solution. Pour one to two drops over the single ribbon with the help of pipette and wait for 30 seconds, rinse it with the DCM so that molecules do not aggregate.

Fig. 3.13: Molecules used for deposition on graphene.

4. Results and Discussion

This chapter deals with the characterization of the devices by electrical measurements from room to low temperature and Raman spectroscopy. Part A will address the behavior of non-functionalized devices while part B will present first results on functionalization with molecules.

Part A

4.1 Electrical measurements:

We performed 2 probe and 4 probe measurements on different samples. Here we will present the electrical measurements on a single ribbon and then a crossbar, firstly at room temperature and then at low temperature.

4.1.1 Room temperature measurements

4.1.1.1 Single ribbon device

In the introduction we already discussed the characteristics of the curve for the 2D electron system. Here we make two observations

- (i) The Dirac neutrality point is not located exactly at 0 volt.
- (ii) The curve is not symmetric and there is hysteresis in the curve.

Figure4.1: Typical characteristics of single ribbon performed by 2 probe DC measurements while arrows show the gate voltage sweep sign evidencing a hysteresis and two Dirac points To save the dielectric from breakdown we did not apply higher voltages. While arrows are showing the sign of sweeping voltage and maxima of the curve is showing Dirac neutrality point.

The shift of Dirac neutrality point is due to impurities present in graphene. Dopants shift the Fermi level out from Dirac neutrality point and hence we have to apply the gate voltage to compensate the charges of dopants. Asymmetry of the curve is due to slightly different contacts between the Ti/Au and graphene (B. Huard 2008) and also due to different velocities of electrons and holes as seen from fig.4 1.. Electron mobility in the above sample is found to be 990

$\text{cm}^2/(\text{V}\cdot\text{s})$, which is very less as compared to mentioned mobility of graphene in literature (A.K Geim 2004) and the way to find mobility is that we fit the curve as shown by blue line as shown in fig. 4.2.

Figure 4.2: showing the fit of the curve for 2 probe AC measurements while table on right side showing the data excluded from this curve, here blue line is the fit of the curve and mobility for this device is $2765 \text{cm}^2/\text{Vs}$.

From fig. 4.3 we notice that the Dirac neutrality point is different for the two samples (sample a 39 Volts, sample b 73 Volts). This leads to confirm that sample b is highly doped as compared to sample a. although doping in the sample b is very high as compared to sample a but mobility in sample b ($2000 \text{cm}^2/\text{Vs}$) is higher as compared to sample a ($1300 \text{cm}^2/\text{Vs}$), which is quite unusual because dopants generally decrease the quality of graphene so its mobility should be less as compared to a.

Figure 4.3: Typical characteristics curve for single ribbon graphene (mm size) for two different samples prepared from two different batches of graphene grown by us, these curves are plotted for a single gate sweep for the sake of clarity. Curves have been obtained for the DC mode by using the two probe method.

4.1.1.1 Cross bar

Now we have seen the features of single ribbon electronic properties, we shall turn to the specific ones of the crossbar geometry. We performed 2 probe and 4 probe measurements on crossbar devices. So for this we propose a simple

equivalent circuit to represent the crossbar as shown in fig.4.4. There are 6 different parameters to measure (four resistances involving two different ribbons and two resistances within the same ribbon).

Figure4.4: A simple sketch of the crossbar device. The different colors used will be used in the next graphs to plot the resistance curve accordingly. Here S is denoting the region of interest i.e. intersection of two ribbons.

In fig.4.4a, Out of six possible combinations to probe ($R_{12}, R_{31}, R_{24}, R_{34}, R_{23}, R_{14}$) we probed 4 combinations in the first device and 3 combinations in the second device because the other contacts were very resistive, also most of cases we find that whenever we are on two different ribbons we have higher mobility as compared as on the same ribbon mostly the ratio is 5:1, e.g. the ratio of the mobility of R_{34} to R_{21} is 4.9:1.

So we can say that mobility is very high when we are on the different layer as compared to the one when we are on the same ribbon, reasons are not very clear to us yet, but due to the interlayer region, tunneling of electrons from one ribbon to the other one along with screening of the gate effect by the bottom layer can lead to original field effect. Depending upon our understanding we have also proposed a very simple model, which is discussed in the later part of this chapter. In fig. 4.5b R_{24} has high mobility which is not always the case, here the mobility in this case was in the same ratio, we found mobility in this case $2000 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V.s}$ which is higher than even when we are different ribbons because may be out of two ribbons one is very resistive and other one is less resistive.

Figure 4.5: Electrical measurements for two different crossbar devices. Rectangle boxes are showing which terminals has been probed using fig. 4 as a model. All measurements are done in AC mode.

4.1.2 Low temperature measurements

Excited from the results that we got from last paragraph we decided to cool down our system because material properties change drastically at very low temperature Unfortunately we found that all sample prepared by us were either leaky (breakdown of dielectric due to scratching the dielectric by tip or by applying too high electric field) or very resistive (~ 100 k Ω to few M Ω due to the problems related to CVD growth reported earlier) and so would become insulator at low temperature. So we started our measurements on the single ribbon to get the blank characteristics.

Figure 4.6 color scale plot is showing resistance of single ribbon versus gate voltage and temperature for a fixed bias voltage of 0.4 V. A vertical cut at 25K is shown on the left graph.

In fig.4.6 we draw a vertical line which means that we are keeping the temperature constant and then we get curve represented on left side which is having same characteristics as shown in fig .4.3a) and if we move this vertical line throughout the graph we will get the same characteristics so we concluded that there is no pronounced effect on resistance while decreasing temperature .

Then we did map of V_{bias} versus and gate voltage while varying temperature from 6K to 300K.

Figure 4.7: Variation of conductance with gate voltage at various temperatures, while applied bias voltage is 0.4 Volt. Inlet of graph is showing mobility variation with temperature.

It is clear from fig.4.7 that conductance increases as we increase the temperature. Talking about the inlet curve it also follows the same trend as conductivity except at temperature near to 150K, which may be an artifact of the experiment.

Both increases of the conductivity and mobility with temperature may be explained by the fact that at low temperature electrons and holes both have very low energy so the scattering sites become more efficient which adds to the decrease in the conductivity. However it is striking to note that this decrease remains small which means that the scattering sites are in low density and the sample remains mostly a semimetal.

4.2 Raman spectroscopy:

Electrical transport provides info about the quality of graphene. Complementary information can be obtained from the vibrational properties using Raman spectroscopy

4.2.1 Cross bar

Taking the model of crossbar shown in fig. 4.4, Raman spectroscopy over top ribbon, bottom ribbon and in the intersection of two ribbons where the intensity is double as compared to top ribbon and bottom ribbon as shown in fig. 4.8 a.,.Also we can see that there is huge D band in all the three regions (*i.e.* our device is very defected). Now what does it means?

As discussed earlier the origin of D band indicates the defects present in the graphene but intensity in S region is twice as compared to other regions (1, 2) which indicates that there must be something interesting in the S region. As reported in literature (A.C.Ferrari 2006) by using 2D band ($\sim 2700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of graphene we can determine the number of layers of graphene. For monolayer graphene FWHM (Full Width at Half Maximum) found to be 24 cm^{-1} in 2D band exactly as shown in fig. 4.8b and also it has been reported that for bilayer graphene with AB stacking, the spectra is fitted with four lorentzian, each with FWHM 24 cm^{-1} (L.M.Malard 2009) which is seemed to be the case as shown in fig.4.8b.,it

is quite clear from these observation is that in S region we have unconventionally (stacked deliberately as in our case) stacked bilayer ,while other regions(1,2) are monolayer.

Figure 4.8: Raman spectra on the 3 regions (1, 2, S) of crossbar where the regions are depicted in fig. 3, here the different colors correspond to the different regions. a) Brackets showing FWHM for D band and G band for the 3 different regions. b) Raman spectra for 2D band of graphene and their FWHM for 3 different regions of the same sample.

4.3 Modelization

Now we investigate the physical phenomena at the intersection of the two layers, so we propose a simple model, which is depicted by fig.4.9. First of all we have to understand the various terms involved there:

- (i) R_c (contact resistance) arises from the Schottky barrier between the graphene (semimetal) and gold (metal) due to their different work function (energy required to remove an electron from the material), but it can be removed by using four probe method (used to measure the sheet resistance).
- (ii) R_G (Graphene resistance) arises due to inherent property of material and here it is given by general names R_{Gi} (i varies from 1 to 4) Depending in the device geometry and the graphene uniformity, these resistance can be very similar or not.
- (iii) R_T (Tunnel resistance) arises due tunneling of electron between below and above ribbons.
- (iv) C (capacitance) because of parallel ribbons (intersection region) having empty space (few nm) in between them, just behaving like parallel plate capacitor with dielectric (vacuum if the sample is clean) between them.

Figure 4.9: Theoretical model for the proposed cross bar, where R_C (shown by yellow color) is contact resistance, R_G is resistance of graphene (sheet resistance shown by red color), R_T is tunneling resistance and C is the capacitance. . a) Visualization of the cross bar. b) Circuit diagramme for the device

Now depending upon the uniformity of graphene *i.e.* resistance and dimension (length and width) we have two cases.

Case (i) when graphene is uniform in resistance and dimensions. Then we have $R_{G1}=R_{G2}=r1$ and $R_{G3}=R_{G4}=r2$ { $r1$ and $r2$ are different due to different coupling to the substrate} which are gate dependent and other unknowns are C and R_T , so we have 4 unknowns ($r1, r2, C, R_T$).

Case (ii) When graphene is not uniform in resistance(defect) and dimensions. Then we have 6 unknowns $R_{G1}, R_{G2}, R_{G3}, R_{G4}, C, R_T$

Now it will be interesting to extract the tunneling resistance and the capacitance in between the two layers so what we are going to do that we will deposit the first ribbon then measure its resistance after that we will deposit the second ribbon to make cross bar (as shown in fig.3.8d) and keeping eye over the change in the resistance of the below ribbon, also we will be using all possible combinations (*i.e.* applying current across the 1,3 ribbon and voltage across 2,4 and then applying current to 2,3 and measuring voltage across 1,4.this makes 6 possible combinations) and assuming if resistance and capacitance are in series then we can write.

$Z = \sqrt{(R_{G_i} + R_{G_j} + R_T)^2 + (1/wC)^2}$, where assuming inductance L is neglected to make the calculation simple where i and j varies from 1 to 4 (depending upon which position we are) and since we have 6 unknowns and 6 equations, we should be able to measure the R_T and C . At that stage, more experiments need to be done to manage data fitting.

Part B

In this part we deposited the molecules over single ribbon and did Raman spectroscopy). Till now we have tried four molecules (i)TPyOs, TPPZn, TPPNi and TPPH₂ over the single ribbon.

4.4 Signature of the molecules

In figure4.10 we observe sharp Raman modes corresponding to TPyOs molecules while strong fluorescence is observed for TPPZn. Here this Raman spectra is made on the powder place on glass plate.

Figure 4.10 Raman spectra of the molecule powder at 532 nm: a) for TPyOs, various peaks correspond to Raman active modes present in the molecule and their corresponding Raman shifts are shown in boxes. b) TPPZn shows huge fluorescence overwhelming Raman features in the spectrum:

We also tested TPPH₂ and PNiΦNH₂ molecules from the same family. The characteristics are not shown here as we obtained specific Raman features for PNiΦNH₂ and strong fluorescence background for TPPH₂. Because of the strong fluorescence, TPPZn and TPPH₂ were discarded from the deposition step.

4.5 Molecules on Graphene

We started with m/1000 (as prepared in chapter 3) concentration solution and deposited it over the single ribbon. We can see from fig. 4.11(b) that there is net decrease in intensity after the molecule deposition but there is no shift in the position. We can say that probably there is not much molecule attached to the graphene as frequencies in fig.4.11b) corresponds to 1341.1cm⁻¹ and 1596.8cm⁻¹ which are D and G band frequencies for pristine graphene and no characteristic peak from the molecule can be detected. But there is decrease in intensity after the molecule deposition which may be due to the displacement of scanning position before and after the molecule deposition

Figure 4.11 a) 100x optical image of the single ribbon after the first molecule deposition ($m/2$ concentration as mentioned in previous chapter) while contrast difference shows the graphene ribbon edge and Si/SiO₂ substrate (green line showing the edge of ribbon while spectrum has been taken at the cross position), b) Comparison of Raman spectra of before and after molecule deposition.

After that we used $m/100$ solution over the single ribbon and fig 4.12a clearly shows clusters over the graphene ribbon, from fig. 4.12b it is clear that all the peaks are preserved, which means the molecule is not damaged by the deposition process.

Figure 4.12 a) 100x optical image of graphene ribbon with molecule ($m/100$ conc.) while difference in contrast shows the edge of graphene over the Si substrate. b) Comparison of Raman spectra before and after the molecule deposition, in graph we have shown only the frequency range which corresponds to the signature of the molecule.

We see that there is no interaction between the graphene and the molecules attached and increase in Raman intensity may be due to that we are not on the same scan position. It is quite interesting to note that in fig 4.11b) we saw the decrease in intensity after molecule deposition but in fig. 4.12b) we saw that there is increase in the Raman intensity. To get rid of this problem we did Raman map at the frequency which corresponds to the molecule signature (1026 cm⁻¹, 1471cm⁻¹ two intense peaks in Raman spectra of molecule) and D band (1341 cm⁻¹) of graphene as shown in fig.4.13. Here the color scale in fig. 4.1311 indicates the intensity of Raman signal, higher intensity means that there is signal from molecules or from and same is the case with graphene D band (1341 cm⁻¹) where we can see the clearly edge of graphene ribbon because in c we are now measuring the Raman shift corresponding to the graphene D band.

Figure 4.13: Raman mapping: a) and b) showing the map for the frequency corresponding to molecule signature (1026 cm^{-1} , 1471 cm^{-1}) and c) showing Raman spectra corresponding 1341 cm^{-1} , while color scale represents the intensity of Raman signal, and green line shows the boundary.

Between the 2 extreme as shown above we have tried different concentrations and deposition processes and none is working, means that the grafting is not efficient for this molecule compared to the TbPc2 from the literature from we were inspired((Manuel Lopes 2010)), maybe because of its structure. So the next step would be to change the structure by adding aliphatic chains or a pyren group to enhance its affinity to graphene.

5. Conclusions and Perspectives

This thesis provides a general overview starting from the CVD growth of graphene to the graphene based devices (cross bar and graphene hybrids) and the transport measurement of the device. We used Raman spectroscopy to tell the quality and number of layers of graphene and also as a measurement system to characterize the molecules on graphene for graphene hybrid system

Graphene being an exceptional material, we fabricated a novel device which we called crossbar and we showed that during transport measurements at room temperature, we have high mobility when we are on different ribbon as compared to when we are on the same ribbon. We also proposed a very simple theoretical model to understand the physical phenomena occurring in the intersection of two layers.

We also tried to make graphene hybrid system by depositing the molecules (optically and electrically active) over the single ribbon graphene, till now we have not succeeded because it seems that molecules that we have used have no interaction with graphene. New molecules have been synthesized by collaborators which are expected to have stronger affinity with graphene.

In the future we will measure the transport properties of crossbar at very low temperature; also we want to compare our theoretical model with experimental results at low temperature as well as room temperature to see that they are in agreement with each other or not and then to modify the theoretical model on the basis of this.

In near future we will also work on more advanced graphene hybrid systems by depositing the molecule in the intersection of two ribbons and measurements will be shining light of different wavelength while measuring the transport properties of this system. We expect to be able to detect the molecule excitation through electronic transport measurement of the device.

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